

Abstract and Keywords

Abstract

This research focuses on the possible future of the EU as a global player on the geopolitical scenario and it will be analysed the trajectory and projections as unitary global actor. Although the project of a united Europe had already been theorized in the nineteenth century with thinkers such as Victor Hugo or Mikhail Bakunin. But it was only after the catastrophe of the Second World War, when the European countries lost the role of world leaders in favor of the two new emerging power (USA and USSR) that the idea of a politically united Europe was seriously reconsidered and concreted with the creation of the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC).

Since the end of the Cold War, the European Union has been committed to creating a common policy in the fields of economy, development, aid, civil peacebuilding and crisis management. Nevertheless, the EU is still far from being considered a unitary global player, especially in the military field, strongly influenced by NATO, which does not allow the Union to become a major player in global security. The aim of my research is to demonstrate that the European Union, although it resembles in many ways a federation of states thanks to its political and economic functions regulated at a legal level by Community law, is still a supranational organisation and not a state, which severely limits the creation of a common foreign policy. For the empirical demonstration, I will explain in the course of the research, the functioning of the EU's foreign and defence policy and above all of what contributed, more than anything else, to casting shadows on the EU's real operational capacity to protect its borders, were the crises in Bosnia and Yugoslavia which showed that there was no complete coincidence between the EU's security and defence intentions and means.

Finally, I'll explain how the gradual internal transformation and the attempt to respond to external challenges also explains the specificities of the Union as an international actor: what might be bizarre but at the same time unique features for a supranational organisation, with great resources of power in the economic sphere and permanent weaknesses in the political sphere, as a result of its history.

Keywords: Europe, European Union, Foreign Policy, United States, NATO, Balkans, Supranational organisation.

Resumen

Esta investigación se centra en el posible futuro de la UE como actor global en el escenario geopolítico y se analizará la trayectoria y las proyecciones como actor global unitario. Aunque el proyecto de una Europa unida ya se había teorizado en el siglo XIX con pensadores como Víctor Hugo o Mijaíl Bakunin. Pero sólo después de la catástrofe de la Segunda Guerra Mundial, cuando los países europeos perdieron el papel de líderes mundiales en favor de las dos nuevas potencias emergentes (EE.UU. y la URSS), la idea de una Europa políticamente unida se reconsideró seriamente y se concretó con la creación de la Comunidad Europea del Carbón y del Acero (CECA).

Desde el final de la Guerra Fría, la Unión Europea se ha comprometido a crear una política común en los ámbitos de la economía, el desarrollo, la ayuda, la consolidación de la paz civil y la gestión de crisis. Sin embargo, la UE está aún lejos de ser considerada un actor global unitario, especialmente en el ámbito militar, fuertemente influenciado por la OTAN, lo que no permite a la Unión convertirse en un actor principal en la seguridad global. El objetivo de mi investigación es demostrar que la Unión Europea, aunque se asemeja en muchos aspectos a una federación de Estados gracias a sus funciones políticas y económicas reguladas a nivel jurídico por el derecho comunitario, sigue siendo una organización supranacional y no un Estado, lo que limita mucho la creación de una política exterior común. Para la demostración empírica, explicaré en el transcurso de la investigación, el funcionamiento de la política exterior y de defensa de la UE y sobre todo de lo que contribuyó, más que nada, a arrojar sombras sobre la capacidad operativa real de la UE para proteger sus fronteras, fueron las crisis de Bosnia y Yugoslavia que demostraron que no había una coincidencia total entre las intenciones y los medios de seguridad y defensa de la UE.

Por último, explicaré cómo la progresiva transformación interna y el intento de responder a los retos externos explican también las especificidades de la Unión como actor internacional: lo que podrían ser rasgos particulares, pero al mismo tiempo únicos para una organización supranacional, con grandes recursos de poder en el ámbito económico y permanentes debilidades en el ámbito político, como consecuencia de su historia.

Palabras Clave: Europa, Unión Europea, Política Exterior, OTAN, Balcanes, Organización supranacional.

Abbreviations

- (APEC) Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation.
- (ASEAN) Association of Southeast Asian Nations.
- (AU) African Union.
- (CFSP) Common Foreign and Security Policy.
- (CSDP) Common Security and Defence Policy.
- (DG RELEX) The Directorate-General for the External Relations.
- (EAEC) European Atomic Energy Community.
- (ECSC) European Coal and Steel Community.
- (EDC) European Defence Community.
- (EEAS) European External Action Service.
- (EEC) European Economic Community.
- (EMU) Economic and Monetary Union.
- (ENI) Ente Nazionale Idrocarburi.
- (EU) European Union.
- (EUROFOR) European Rapid Operational FORCE.
- (FDA) Food and Drug Administration.
- (GDPR) General Data Protection Regulation.
- (MERCOSUR) Mercado Común del Sur.
- (NATO) North Atlantic Treaty Organization.
- (OECD) Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- (OSCE) Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe.
- (PSC) Political and Security Committee.
- (SEA) Single European Act.
- (US) United States.

(USA) United States of America.

(USSR) Union of Soviet Socialist Republics.

(WEU) Western European Union.

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Introduction

The establishment of State-entities or parastatal entities covering the entire European territory can be traced back to historical periods well before the founding of the EU. The first such entity was the Roman Empire, which, however, did not share the same geographical extension as the Union, as it was centred on the Mediterranean Sea.

Pan-European political thought, however, really emerged during the 19th century, inspired by the liberal ideas of the French and American revolutions following the end of Napoleon's Empire (1804-1815). In the decades following the Congress of Vienna, the ideals of European unity flourished across the continent, notably in the writings of Wojciech Jastrzębowski called *About the everlasting peace between the nations (1831)* whose draft consisted of 77 articles and where the United States of Europe he envisioned was an international organisation rather than a superstate, as conceived by us today. The Italian Giuseppe Mazzini, on the other hand, contributed to the creation of the “Giovine Europa” (Young Europe in Italian), an international political association aimed to promote the independence and emancipation of peoples from subjection to absolutist european regimes. Formed on 15 April 1834, it lasted until 1836 and represented one of the first organically conceived attempts to create an efficient democratic organisation with a supranational character. These audacious attempts by the Italian patriot did not produce any concrete results, at least not in the short and medium term, and even gave Mazzini the opportunity to be criticised for being too idealistic, due to the fact that during that phase of his political activity little attention was paid to the concrete contents and objectives to be proposed to the people and the militants.

However, the idea only began to gain popularity after the two world wars, driven by the determination to quickly complete the reconstruction of Europe and eliminate the possibility of new and future conflicts between its nations. Exemplary in this regard was the Ventotene Manifesto, drafted by liberals such as Ernesto Rossi, Eugenio Colorni, but also by communists such as Altiero Spinelli in 1941 and published in 1944.

This Manifesto points out how the principles born of the League of Nations after the First World War had been lost, leaving room for the imperialist nationalism of the powers. How democratic orders had been emptied of their meaning, leaving room for plutocrats and monopolists. How the critical scientific spirit had been replaced by new materialist faiths. The three intellectuals foresaw the fall of totalitarian powers and hoped that, after the traumatic experiences of the first half of the 20th century, the people would be able to escape the underhand manoeuvres of the conservative elites. According to them, the aim of the conservative elites would be to re-establish the pre-war order. To counter these forces, a supranational European force was to be founded, in which wealth was to be redistributed

and government was to be decided on the basis of elections by universal suffrage. The organisation of this force was to be based on an economic-political 'third way', which would avoid the mistakes of capitalism and communism, and which would allow the democratic order and the self-determination of peoples to take on concrete value. Although Altiero Spinelli is later mentioned as one of the founding fathers of the European Union, the current EU is quite different from the theoretical Europe that should have arisen according to the ideals of the Ventotene Manifesto.

Relevant for the purpose of this research is the in-depth examination of the history and origins of the UE, the important innovation of the *Maastricht Treaty*, with the creation of the three pillars of the European Union, made with the intention of creating political union, in order to add power to the Community in the areas of foreign policy, a common security policy and legal co-operation. In 2007, the Member States signed the Treaty of Lisbon, which made far-reaching changes to the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community. Compared to the previous treaty, the Treaty of Nice, it abolishes the so-called three pillars, provides for the division of competences between the Union and the Member States, strengthens the democratic principle and the protection of fundamental rights, and gives the Charter of Nice the same legal value as the Treaties. With the entry into force of the Treaty establishing a single Common Security Council, member states were thus obliged to demonstrate loyalty and cooperation in planning objectives and principles such as the defence of common values, the integrity of the Union and the promotion of international cooperation in agreement with the other member states of the union. In my research, I will trace the origins of EU foreign policy, its limits and, finally, its future prospects as a global actor. Since the study of the Common Foreign Security Policy and Common Security and Defence Policy involves, in addition to many factors that are also difficult to monitor, an equally large number of political and institutional actors involved, it was decided to delimit the field of research to three macro-themes: the first theoretical framework for understanding the history of the EU and what has been theorized on this organization until now. The second part will explain his structure, the communitarian foreign policy and what has been done so far in the field of international relations. The third theoretical part includes the history of the Yugosphere, a neologism created in 2009 by Tim Judah, the Economist's expert on the Balkans, indicating the increasing rapprochement between the countries of the former Yugoslavia. This theory is extremely important for the final thesis, because if we consider the difficult ethnic context in which the Balkans found themselves until a few years ago, it seems almost paradoxical that these countries are trying to put into practice a model of regional integration similar to the European one theorised by Duchêne, with supranational institutions, joint trade policies, joint railway company, or the creation of trade chains such as Mercator, which manage distribution not on a national territorial basis, but on a macro-regional basis, that of the former Yugoslavia and its former

sphere of influence. The conclusion will therefore be a hypothesis on the future of the European Union, its path of consolidation as a sui generis civil power and in order to understand the special characteristics of the EU's external relations, it is necessary to look at how they have gradually defined themselves and changed as the integration process has progressed. The final thesis therefore rejects any theory that claim a hypothetical United States of Europe as a single multinational state, as this is currently impossible except through the complete cession of sovereignty by the member states or by a violent or authoritarian turn that would forcibly annex the Eurozone states.

1.Methodology

A descriptive approach has been chosen, studying global geopolitical dynamics, with a particular focus on European geopolitical issues, on the basis of both quantitative and qualitative data.

The aim of my research is precisely to demonstrate the possible future developments of the European Union on the basis of these four simple statements:

1. Since the EU is not a state, it cannot be considered a power.
2. The European Union does not possess the strategic autonomy to implement a truly incisive and communitarian foreign policy.
3. Although not a state, the EU is capable of influencing through the soft power, using the economic and legal integration in order to influence other states and making it a unique actor, therefore sui generis.
4. European integration responds to the interests of states and advances to the extent that the interests of states are satisfied.

The final part of my work offers a series of subjective but well-founded conclusions on the possible future development of a European Union as a unitary global actor.

To find as many sources as possible, I've chosen to consult a wide variety of documents such as books, international political journals, academic essays, newspapers but also documentaries were used in order to have a work as detailed as possible.

In particular, I have focused on those theoretical contributions that allow the reader to provide a comprehensive perspective on the current path taken by the European Union, thus from the theories of the first founding fathers to the modern and contemporary theories developed by academics and analysts such as Duchêne or Bradford.

After analysing the theoretical framework and the various theories concerning the European Union, I used the Balkan issue as a case study.

The Balkan issue shows us not only the limits of the EU's foreign and defence policy, but also how the theories of sovereignty in the theoretical part are also applicable in the Balkan area, which has developed a model of regional integration similar to the European one.

In addition, in formulating the final thesis, I've took the example of Spain and Poland in order to help myself to demonstrate how economic integration works.

The case of Spain and Poland gives us two important empirical examples of how economic integration can helps states to increase their economic and political capacity, despite of the loss of sovereignty in

some sectors, according to Putnam perspective, while the case of Croatia is useful to formulate a hypothesis on the future of European economic integration.

Finally, after analysing the various theories of European sovereignty, I will formulate a final hypothesis on the future of the European Union as a geopolitical actor.

To carry out this research I used sources that can be considered both primary and secondary, allowing us to analyse as objectively as possible the potentials geopolitical repercussions of a Europe as a unitary global actor.

1.2 Is the European Union a global unitary actor?

The main question on which the whole research is focused is surely this: is the European Union a unified global actor? If not, how can it become one?

As things stand at present, The EU is already a global actor in international relations, but only partially. Only partially means that the European Union exerts enormous influence in certain areas such as economics, law and diplomacy, but has no real strategic autonomy in the field of foreign policy and it cannot be considered unitary because its policies are not uniform and universally shared by all member states. But even below this ambitious goal, the political effort required of European leaders is enormous. They must be prepared to give up the national primacy of foreign and security policy in order to build a shared amalgam in which they all recognise themselves, in the knowledge that none of the member states would be able to make a difference on its own.

If we want a practical example, we have only to think about the recent handling of vaccines, where on the one hand there were the great powers such as China, Russia and the USA, which pursued their policies on vaccines independently. Instead, the European states decided to delegate the distribution to the European institutions, which generated a lot of controversy from the member states, who considered the EU's management of vaccines to be ineffective. We should consider one fundamental thing: the European Union is not a state, but a group of states competing for resources that they manage jointly in this huge organisation called the European Union.

Within this organisation there are the states, the real players of the game, who compete with each other in this sort of "arena" in which they hope to obtain resources that they would not otherwise have. However, the desire to have a common political and economic vision was the driving force behind the establishment of the European Union, but this community vision has so far not been fully realised, due to decision-making delays that have often taken the form of real immobility. This slowness stems from the multipolarity of the centres of power in the European Union, poles that diverge along their own path as individual countries prioritise their own interests over those of the community.

Returning to the subject of vaccines, the most powerful countries (USA, China, Russia) are doing much better by managing the supply of vaccines nationally, rather than delegating to an international organisation like the EU.

The main advantage for the countries listed above has been to have a local supply chain, that the production of the vaccine is in fact nationally owned, not in a Marxist sense, but simply that the vaccine is owned by the community and the national industry so that they can make their mark in

negotiations. If we consider that more than 70% of the vaccines that are out in the world are made by countries member of the Eurozone, but very few are destined for European countries, this makes us think about the *modus operandi* of the European Union: the diplomatic and legal approach that is often used by the EU represents the total absence of negotiating and military power, as economic power is not necessary in certain areas.

Public opinion has been surprised when the EU has obtained extremely uncertain contracts on the supply of vaccines. This is because the absence of power of negotiations, that lead the interlocutor to not accept the terms if the EU imposed its own conditions.

An example of this is the case of the German-American company Biotech, which received funding from the German government and the European Union, but despite the fact that the US government did not allocate any money to the company, at the end of December 2020 Biotech chose the FDA (Food and Drug Administration), an American government institution, as its main interlocutor.

This is because, as mentioned above, in this case Biotech had no other option but to negotiate with the US government as the latter is a global player with far greater negotiating power than the pharmaceutical company in question.

We can consider the European Union as an actor but not a unitary one because we cannot consider it a State.

Can an international entity with such a complex and constantly changing shape play a relevant role in international politics? And in what way?

While we cannot deny the unquestionable limitations of the EU, it would be a serious mistake not to recognise it as having an important role in international geopolitics.

The EU has the peculiarity of being both a sort of geopolitical laboratory of the transformation of political space in the contemporary era, but also a possible model of regional integration, and finally an actor in international politics. To each of these roles are associated capacities and limitations.

Taking into account precisely these three roles that the European Union has, I will develop my research by giving various hypotheses on how the European Union can face its consolidation path as a *sui generis* power.

2.Theoretical framework

External and internal expectations grew when the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) was incorporated into the *Maastricht Treaty* in 1992 and became a fundamental element in the institutional framework of the European Union. It was expected that the European Union would be able to bridge the gap between its growing economic strength and its lack of political power, but unfortunately this expectation has not been fulfilled. It can be seen that even after almost 30 years of continuous programmes of actions and efforts, the sphere of European foreign policy has failed to make great strides in the European landscape, creating rifts within the Union itself on issues such as Kosovo.

The wide variety of initiatives promoted in this sphere have always been imperfect, and based on contingent decisions, originated by the necessity of the moment, neglecting the primary objectives of the European Foreign Policy. Although the last amendment to the *Lisbon Treaty* put the emphasis on the development of a common and coherent European approach towards foreign and security policy, restructuring and strengthening the already existing CFSP and establishing new horizons of action, both theoretical and practical, they seem to have failed: both policies, CFSP and CSDP, seem to have reached a critical point that makes the future direction of the European Union in this field uncertain. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the Common Security and Defence Policy, the most contested, but a fundamental element of the CFSP.

These reflections highlight the rigidity of the CFSP in the face of rapid changes in the international panorama, which leads one to wonder why the European Union and its member states are unable to cope with them.

States are unable to cope with them adequately. The causes can be ascribed to two specific strands: those which originate and develop within the European Union and those arising from external forces and circumstances. Depending on the theoretical approaches and analytical perspectives used, different outcomes and conclusions can be drawn from this.

Realists and rationalists, theoretical analysts adopting evidently different approaches, have influenced criticism of the problems of the EU's Foreign Security and Defence Policy by mainly emphasising explanatory factors that allow us to understand the internal nature of CSDP. In particular, they allow us to acquire a new and more eloquent analytical framework on which to pursue research on the EU Common Security and Defence Policy by overcoming the tension generated by the debate on the success or failure of CSDP missions. This allows the intrinsic nature of the European Union's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) to emerge, noting the factors responsible for the lack of dynamism that emerged during the wars in former-Yugoslavia and the invasion of Libya in 2011.

In this perspective it is appropriate to consider the methodological aspect that allows us to define and understand the object of the analysis, the CSDP, by examining its guiding principles that determine the acquisition of the theoretical reflections that underlie it.

For a more accurate understanding of CSDP as an object of social and scientific research, it is important to deepen its presentation within European and international studies. The European Security and Defence Policy expresses the European Union's desire to develop military and civilian capabilities in order to expand its power regionally and globally.

Implicitly, the Common European Security and Defence Policy develops a sharing of responsibilities between NATO and the European Union. It emphasizes the desire to establish cooperation so that NATO becomes a more flexible military organisation, allowing EU member states to have more control over unilateral military operations. The complexity of the European Security and Defence Policy requires an analysis at different levels, taking as reference dynamics ranging from bilateral relations such as EU-NATO to specific mechanisms that allow member states to coordinate their foreign, defence and security policies.

2.1 What is a unitary actor?

As mentioned above, the European Union cannot be considered as unitary actor, as it is not a state but simply a forum where nations compete for their national interests.

Moreover, the EU is not even a state actor, as we shall see later the EU is a superpower in the sense that it is the largest political union, single market and aid donor in the world, it is not a superpower in defence or foreign policy, as it is strongly dependent on the United States of America.

The term State has had a modern meaning since the 15th century, and was later established through the use of the term by Niccolò Machiavelli in the incipit of his famous work *The Prince* (1513), in which he uses it as a term analogous to domination. The concept of sovereignty was instead introduced by Jean Bodin in 1586, who defined the characteristics of the absolute state.

With John Locke, in his *Second Treatise on Government* (1690), a conception of the State was elaborated, not as an absolute, but as a functional entity legitimised solely by the defence of the individual freedoms inherent to the person. In the same work, Locke also made a fundamental contribution to constitutionalism by formulating the modern concept of popular sovereignty.

In the period of formation of the modern state in Europe, the concept of the state as a legitimate monopolist of the use of force through the constitution of regular armed forces fed by compulsory military service, and endowed with a bureaucratic, police apparatus, was affirmed.

3.Theories on sovereignty and power of EU

3.1 Classic theories

Niccolò Machiavelli

Paraphrasing Machiavelli's Prince, the strength of the survival of any state is linked to the strength of the exercise of its power, and therefore it must hold the legitimate monopoly of violence, to ensure internal security and to prevent a potential external war.

Reasoning on Machiavelli's writing, a state is born from the monopoly of violence, but if there is no violence, then there is no state. Above all, we cannot consider the EU a superpower in its classical meaning, because to be a superpower you first have to be a state.

There is no modern state in history that was born without the use of violence. This is a fundamental factor, since the European Union, not being a state entity and not having direct military control over a given territory, has no strategic autonomy to act as a unitary actor. The European Union does not yet have an independent European army, as the European states themselves are under American influence and consequently subordinate to NATO, which remains the EU's main strategic partner.

John Locke

With John Locke, in his *Second Treatise on Government* (1690), a conception of the State was elaborated, not as an absolute, but as a functional entity legitimised solely by the defence of the individual freedoms inherent to the person. In this same work, Locke also makes a fundamental contribution to constitutionalism by formulating the modern concept of popular sovereignty. Locke's political thought is closely linked to the tormented English events of the seventeenth century, during which the clash between crown and parliament gave rise to two revolutions (1642 and 1688), the first of which was accompanied by civil war. If in this clash Hobbes took the side of the crown, elaborating the first rationalistic theory of absolutism, Locke took the side of parliament, elaborating the first great modern liberal theory. Common to both thinkers is the natural law model, hinging on the dichotomy between the state of nature and the civil or political state, and on the pact as a means of moving from the former to the latter. This model is, however, declined in very different ways. For Locke, the state of nature is not a state of war, but a state of peace, benevolence and mutual assistance: men cooperate with each other and establish various relations (family, trade and so on), giving rise to a kind of “natural society”. The limitation of Locke's state of nature is the absence of judges capable of resolving possible disputes: the individual, if his rights are violated by another, has the right to take justice into his own hands, but in doing so, since no one is a good judge in the case that concerns him, he will in turn offend the offender, initiating a conflict that cannot be concluded. Locke also theorised about the separation of powers: the legislative power lies with the parliament, elected by the citizens who have the right to do so, while the executive power lies with the king. In this way he wanted to guarantee the balancing and mutual control of powers that constitutes a barrier against despotism and a further guarantee for the freedom of citizens. In Locke's writings we finally find an innovative theory of property, which for the first time in social and political thought makes it something dynamic, the result of human effort and activity. If it is true, Locke observes, that the earth has been given to men in common, as it is written in the Bible, it is equally true that the property of the person is strictly individual: and just as each person possesses his body and mind individually, so will he possess all that the work of his hands and intelligence can provide for him. By his labour, man takes goods from the common state in which they were originally found and adds something individual to them, which thus justifies private property, which already arises in the state of nature.

Michail Bakunin

Excluding the purely social part of Bakunin's work *Statism and Anarchy* (1873) where he considers the anarchist doctrine as an ideal social model, Bakunin, in which he exposes his position with respect to the world of his time: the Europe of the late nineteenth century, from the point of view of a Russian thinker and anarchist. His interest in the fate of the Slavic world and his concern for the contrast between Pan-Germanism and Panslavism is evident in Russia. But his interest is generally in the whole world, with particular attention to that Europe in social ferment. At the first congress of the League for Peace and Freedom, which was an organisation promoting European pacifism and federalism, founded in Geneva in 1867 by the Saint-Simonian Charles Lemonnier.

At the first congress held in Geneva, Michael Bakunin presented a proposal to the organisation's Central Committee: "Federalism, socialism, anti-theologism".

His "confused" eurocentrism manifested itself in a wish for the creation of a United States of Europe, on the US model.

However, it must also be understood that Bakunin was a man of his time and that his Eurocentrism and the term he used "United States of Europe" was probably referring to the revolutionary republicans who wanted a continental collaboration between all these anarchist and republican organisations within the International Working Men's Association.

Giuseppe Mazzini

As mentioned in the introduction, Mazzini did not achieve much in the short term, but he made an important contribution to the idea of a united Europe as a single supranational organisation.

He gave an important contribution with a series of articles called *Thoughts upon Democracy in Europe (1846-1847)*.

In the analysis of Mazzini's contributions on Europe, two considerations must always be kept in mind: firstly, the European idea is transformed in the course of Mazzini's life, when he was engaged in readjusting and reorganising philosophy and political practice according to the changing geopolitical conditions in Italy and Europe. Secondly, Mazzini remains a man of the nineteenth century, a century which, with some exceptions such as Carlo Cattaneo, would have realised that concept of a sovereign and independent nation which made it difficult to frame him in a supranational structure.

Carlo Cattaneo

Cattaneo, a democrat and Italian republican, was also a convinced supporter of a federalist vision of the state. According to Cattaneo, only in a federal organisation of the state could social, cultural and religious pluralism, the true wealth of civil society, be expressed. This vision went far beyond the confines of the nation-state, going so far as to prefigure a future European and world order in a federalist sense, based on the affirmation of equality and solidarity between peoples, on freedom and progress. This dream seemed to be coming true in the spring of 1848, when people all over Europe were on the verge of sweeping away the old monocratic and absolutist political structures.

Victor Hugo

In August 1849, at the opening session of the International Peace Conference that he chaired in Paris, Victor Hugo gave an impassioned speech in which he predicted the day when, in his view, the “United States of Europe” would inevitably be born and universal peace would finally be established. Hugo, an advocate of the liberal regime, a supporter of the abolition of the death penalty, sensitive to social problems, in favour of women's equality and convinced that his task as a poet and writer also included a political mission, was then a member of the Constituent Assembly, but only two years later he was forced into a long exile (until 1870) following the coup d'état of the despised Napoleon III. He had been as much an admirer of Bonaparte, who had imagined a single system of laws and the same currency for Europe, as he had been a staunch opponent of his nephew's illiberal policies. At that conference, attended by, Italians, French, English, Dutch and Americans, who had gathered to discuss various points such as the drafting of a code of international relations, the need for progressive disarmament, the elimination of the social and political causes of war, and progress in education and training, his words were greeted by repeated rounds of applause. Hugo was so convinced of the inevitability of that path that he planted the seeds of an oak tree on the island of his exile in Guernsey and prophesied that when it grew, there would be a United States of Europe. As is well known, however, the idea of nationhood would take very different and more complicated paths from those he and others optimistically predicted, so much so that today their thinking appears somewhat naïve, while retaining its ideal strength.

3.2 Modern theories

The Founding Fathers of the European Union

However, the idea of a united Europe took a back seat during the first half of the 20th century.

It was only after the Second World War that European integration, the process of industrial, political, legal and economic integration of all or some of Europe's states through a new European supranational entity, seemed the most logical solution to the extreme nationalisms that had previously devastated the continent. The 1948 Hague Congress was a crucial moment in European federal history, as it led to the creation of the International European Movement and the College of Europe, where future European leaders would live and study together.

It also led directly to the founding of the Council of Europe in 1949, the first major effort to bring together the nations of Europe, initially ten. The Council focused primarily on human and democratic values, rather than economic or trade issues, and was always seen as a forum where sovereign governments could choose to work together, but no supranational authority was delegated.

However, in 1952, the Heads of State of France, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands and the West Germany, find themselves disappointed by the lack of progress in the Council of Europe, and they decided to create the European Coal and Steel Community.

The Treaty of Paris of 18 April 1951 established the European Coal and Steel Community (ECSC), the common market for coal and steel, abolishing the customs barriers and quantitative restrictions that hindered the free movement of these goods, as well as all the measures like aids or subsidies that were granted by the various states to their national production. The principle of free competition made it possible to keep prices as low as possible, while guaranteeing states control over supplies.

Different European politicians such as the French Robert Schuman, the Belgian Paul-Henri Spaak or the Italian Alcide De Gasperi (who together with Spinelli, Adenauer and Monnet, are considered the founding fathers of the modern European Union) understood that coal and steel were the two essential industries for war, and believed that by intertwining the interests of their national industries, a future war between their nations would become much less likely.

In conclusion, behind the purely economic aspect lay the strategic desire to bring together the loser countries of the Second World War as well, so as to control and limit the production of coal and steel in Germany in particular. With the creation of the ECSC, a series of collateral protocols were also signed between the member states on the privileges and immunities of the Community that was being

created, on the status of the Court of Justice and on the Council of Europe, which laid the foundations for what would become the European Union today.

Putnam: Two Levels game

Robert Putnam, Harvard professor of political science, also known as the inventor of the concept of 'social capital', and the theory formulated in 1988: 'two level games', with the publication of the article called *Diplomacy and Domestic Politics: The Logic of Two-Level Games*. In this article, Putnam presents the theory as a proposed analysis to understand the negotiations and decisions made by various state leaders.

According to this theory, governments only engage at the supranational level in those issues that are broadly supported by the electorate, as their primary interest lies in re-election and confirmation in government. On the other hand, international negotiations and institutions modify the national context in which that policy is produced, through the redistribution of political resources. The reallocation of control over national political resources generally favours those who directly preside over their state's participation in international negotiations and institutions.

In short, by delegating some policies to the supranational level, governments can increase rather than decrease their power, because in this way they gain additional resources against their domestic opponents. European integration therefore responds above all to the interests of states and advances to the extent that the interests of states are satisfied.

According to this perspective, foreign policy would remain outside the scope of the communitarisation that characterises trade and monetary policy, because it is incompatible on several levels. Even one of the most influential historians of the 20th century, the historian British Alan Milward, has argued that European integration, far from eroding national sovereignty, has also helped states to recover it through others means (Milward, 1984).

Duchêne: The European Union as civil power

Duchêne was a journalist, political analyst and President of the International Institute for Strategic Studies, one of Britain's most prestigious institutes for international studies. Already in the 1970s, at the height of the internal economic integration process, the then European Economic Community (EEC) was beginning to develop external expertise. It was during these years that François Duchêne, noting the EU's ability to influence its environment by diplomatic, economic and legal means, but in the absence of military instruments, coined the term "civil power". What characterises the EEC as a civil power, according to Duchêne, is the specificity of the instruments used (economic-diplomatic, hence non-military) and the purpose of the action, which is almost always aimed at exporting a model of security and stability similar to that which has developed in the heart of Europe.

The European Union is characterised as a hybrid and mutant entity, a mixture of elements of intergovernmentalism and supranationalism, whose external action is managed by a set of interlocking institutions through a wide range of soft and hard power policies and instruments. François Duchêne was the first to coin the term 'civil power' because, according to the French author, the instruments used by Europe, namely economic and diplomatic instruments, and the aims of action were essentially to export a model of security and stability similar to that which has developed in the heart of Europe (Lucarelli, 2012). Behind all these concepts there is the idea of a power that has peculiar characteristics in the conduct of its foreign policy and a specific international role linked not only to what it does, but to what the Union is and represents. The ways in which these soft power instruments are used favour structural prevention, a systemic approach to conflict prevention and resolution, a tendency towards the creation of institutionalised regulatory frameworks, and a preference for multilateralism over unilateral conduct.

Although many authors define Europe as a "civil power", critics of this theory claim that this is actually due to the fact that the process of European construction is going through a period of stagnation, and there is a risk of a possible decline, due to the emptying of the political content of the EU in favour of an exclusively economic dimension. If the EU really decides to continue to define its identity as a multidimensional, institutionally strong "civil power" with an important role at global level, it needs a project that sees the EU redefine itself and grow, also through a conceptual innovation: a theoretical and methodological innovation of European studies that can significantly contribute to strengthening that initial project that gave the original idea of Europe.

The Union once again proves to be a unique case in contemporary geopolitical history: a supranational power that stands on the global stage as a major actor in cooperation between states, and as a catalyst for development. However, it is worth remembering that in recent years the EU has shown its most

vulnerable side, its greatest limits: from the bad management of the migration crisis to the bad management of vaccines, which casts doubt on the real definition of EU as global power.

Anu Bradford: The Brussels effect

The Brussels effect (2020) is the title of Anu Bradford's book about the global spread of EU-created regulations. It may seem surprising at first glance, but many American farmers produce vegetables without using pesticides, without any US laws prohibiting them. As another example, Facebook has decided to apply the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) on privacy to all its users worldwide after the European Union implemented the privacy law. Market size does not in itself account for a state's ability to transfer its regulatory preferences to others; not every state with a large market becomes a source of global standards. Being a regulatory power is a conscious choice of a state and not something intrinsic to the market itself. The state must strive to create institutions and give it the regulatory capacity to translate its market power into tangible regulatory influence. Regulatory capacity means the ability of a jurisdiction to promulgate and enforce rules. This requires resources and expertise. In the absence of this capacity, a country cannot exercise authority over market participants, within or outside the jurisdiction. An important element of regulatory capacity is the authority to impose sanctions in the event of non-compliance. Regulatory capacity is often closely related to another condition, the propensity to enact stringent regulations, because jurisdictions that have the political will to enact stringent regulations often employ the same will in establishing strong regulatory institutions. However, there are circumstances in which a jurisdiction may want to impose regulation in a specific area where it simply does not have the technical expertise or economic resources to acquire the necessary regulatory capacity: thus, the preference for stringent rules should be considered an independent condition for the occurrence of the Brussels Effect. The level of regulatory capacity severely limits a country's ability to exercise global regulatory authority. For example, many Asian economies have a very high growth rate, yet it will take a long time for the wealth of these states to translate into regulatory expertise on a global scale and the institutional capacity needed to impose rules, in particular, on foreign countries. This is evident in the case of China, where the country's impact on global economic regulation has been limited, despite the availability of vast amounts of capital and ownership of large shares of US public debt. China's limited influence can be partly attributed to the lack of effective and independent bureaucratic institutions overseeing domestic market regulations in this area. The European Union has acquired extensive regulatory capacity, in particular, since the signing of the SEA (Single European Act) in 1986, which set in motion the programme to complete the single market by 1992. In order to achieve this objective, Member States have given extensive powers to the European institutions to formulate and implement market regulations. This ability to promulgate rules and ensure compliance rests on the considerable expertise of the EU institutions, legislative consistency and extensive sanctioning powers. The EU's conscious effort to create a powerful regulatory machine was motivated by the need to foster the

integration process and to complete the single market, objectives that were largely achieved through regulation.

The Macron Doctrine

In November 2020, French President Macron gave the journalists of *Le Grand Continent*, an online geopolitical magazine very active in the debate on the future of Europe, his views on the subject of European autonomy in defence, an undoubtedly hot and topical issue.

Consistent with his basic approach, which is to offer a vision of the Europe of the coming years starting from the concerns of citizens, Macron began by responding to the need for security in times of a high terrorist threat. He proposes that a contingent of soldiers from other European countries should immediately become part of each army, participating in operations from the planning stage, and that a common European intervention force should be founded by 2020. Then a common defence budget and a common political doctrine for military interventions, so that Europe can show itself united and convincing in emergencies, referring to a previously decided framework of action.

In essence, before the end of the Trump presidency, Macron is clamouring for a European army to stand up to Russia, arguing for a sovereign Europe that defends itself, without depending exclusively on the United States for defence.

However, France must also take into account Berlin's mood, as Franco-German relations are at the heart of the EU's complex geopolitical and legal-institutional balance and have recently been embodied in a treaty on Franco-German cooperation and integration, signed in Aachen on 22 January 2019.

President Macron states that there are certain values that distinguish us from North Americans, such as our social democratic state organisation, and our generally more egalitarian societies than those in America. Finally, Macron states that we are projected into another imaginary, linked to Africa, the Near and Middle East, and we have another geography, which may misalign our interests. Although Macron is partly right about these statements, I still find this to be an excessively “French” vision of Europe, as for example a country like Italy, in the current state of affairs, has much more to gain geopolitically with a solid partnership with the United States than a French-led European army. However, the Macron interview must be interpreted for its more general implications, as an overall enunciation of a real Macron doctrine on the future of Europe.

Macron is basically saying that, in order to get out of the crisis situation that Europe is facing because of the pandemic, but also because of the frequent terrorist attacks, Europe and on its behalf the member states and the European Union must, through common strategies, push the frontier of their cooperation and integration further until they reach a true European sovereignty, independent of those

of the individual states, even on the basis of them built, and able to nominate a united Europe to a leading role on the international scene.

An international scene increasingly characterised, as he says, by the crisis of multilateralism, and on which the UE that has overcome its great challenges: the educational, health, digital and ecological, can rightly present itself as a geopolitical player of global relevance.

4. History and origin of European Union foreign policy

The difficulties that European governments had in creating a shared security policy, together with the difficulties in taking agreed decisions on the use of military capabilities, had a negative impact on the perception of the Union as an international actor in the field of foreign and defence policy.

The difficulties that European governments had in creating a shared security policy, together with the difficulties in taking agreed decisions on the use of military capabilities, had a negative impact on the perception of the Union as an international actor in the field of foreign and defence policy. However, it is necessary to recall that the idea of collaboration between member states in strategic security and defence areas goes back to the origins of the EU project, when the six founding countries tried (unsuccessfully) to complement the nascent Economic Community with a European Defence Community (EDC). The impossibility of creating a structured defence system in the absence of a true political union in Europe became even more evident after the establishment of the Western European Union (WEU) in 1954, the failure of which favoured the consolidation of an Atlantic defence system, largely centred on the role of the United States. From the 1970s onwards, the difficulty of acting with a community approach, due to the political divergences of European states, favoured forms of light cooperation, far from transferring governmental competences to supranational institutions.

4.1 The Maastricht Treaty and Three Pillars

It was not until the *Maastricht Treaty* of 1992 that European security and defence policy was regulated more comprehensively, which, in addition to establishing the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP), formalised the birth of the European Security and Defence Policy (CSDP).

The Maastricht Treaty, which was signed on 7 February 1992 and came into force on 1 November 1993, is the founding act of the European Union. Ratified by the then twelve countries of the European Communities, it specifies the political and economic criteria for joining the Union.

Since the early 1980s, the idea of greater political integration has gradually taken hold, going beyond the 1957 Treaties of Rome, which established the EEC (European Economic Community), the ECSC and the EAEC (European Atomic Energy Community). The transition from the EEC, ECSC and EAEC to the European Union was a reflection of the desire to move away from the principle of cooperation between sovereign states towards their progressive political and economic integration. In particular, the reunification of Germany in 1989 and the end of the two-bloc system that had characterised the continent during the Cold War had created the conditions to accelerate this integration process, which was progressively defining the European identity not only politically and economically but also legally and culturally.

The pillar organisation divided the Union's competences into three groups. The first, socio-economic, saw the birth of the European Community, which would incorporate the EEC, ECSC and the European Atomic Energy Community (EAEC). The second and third pillars, respectively Defence and Foreign Policy and Home Affairs and Justice, were based on an intergovernmental approach.

The Maastricht Treaty also introduced the concept of European citizenship, which is enjoyed by all citizens of EU member states. European citizenship grants the right of residence in each member state, the right to vote and stand for election in local elections, and the right to petition the European Parliament on EU matters. The residence permit is not to be confused with the free movement agreements signed in 1986 in Schengen, which came into force later and were integrated into the institutional framework of the Union by the Treaty of Amsterdam in 1997.

In addition to the Maastricht agreements, the European member states of the EMU (Economic and Monetary Union) took an important step towards economic integration: in 1997 they signed the Stability and Growth Pact, thus the possibility of introducing sanctions for countries not in line with the parameters regarding the public budget of the Union.

Looking more in detail at the second pillar, fundamental for the creation of the Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP) as it allows member states to initiate common actions in foreign policy, we

can say with certainty that it is the first real attempt of reform by EU member states to try to create a real Community foreign and security policy, which provided for a stronger cooperation than before, necessary to allow the EU to play a role on the world stage adequate to its weight and to effectively manage geopolitical changes following the end of the Cold War.

The Maastricht agreements have allowed an enormous leap forward in the process of European integration: the birth of the European Community and the progressive absorption of the previous Communities, as well as the birth of the Euro, are historical events that have deeply affected the lives of all Europeans. The Euro is today one of the main world currencies and, despite the debt crisis that has hit the Eurozone, it is now the official currency of 19 of the 28 member states of the European Union. At the same time, however, the treaty has promoted an approach to integration based on functionalism, which today shows all of its limitations. The functionalist approach promotes the gradual unification of certain sectors of European societies, assuming that these unions necessarily lead to the union of other sectors, in a cascade mechanism that should lead to the complete integration of the political, economic and social systems of the member countries.

The CFSP presented itself, naturally with some differences, as a classic example of intergovernmental cooperation, substantially based, as far as its functioning is concerned, on the principle of defense of human rights. Within the EU, the distribution of roles and powers within the second pillar appeared completely different from that which characterized the Communities.

In fact, the entire system of CFSP hinged on the European Council, which had the task of defining the general guidelines, within which the Council of the Union could decide, unanimously, to implement actions and common positions, while the Commission was simply involved in the work and the European Parliament had essentially no say.

In spite of the good proposals, there were too many divergences of views between the member states in the field of foreign policy and security for the second pillar to produce satisfactory results in a short time, therefore, the Union watched, powerless, the bloodshed that occurred in the Balkans in the 90s.

Coordination is possible when member states support EU positions within other International Organizations: this allows member states to show themselves always part of a common European front even if they occupy positions of national representation. However, in the field of Defense, a purely state competence, the differences between the states are still visible, hindering the project of greater integration in this area. In 2009, with the entry into force of the *Lisbon Treaty*, the three-pillar principle was replaced by a division of competences between the European Union and the member states. The principle of subsidiarity, which delimits the scope of the Union's action, plays a key role:

it can intervene in all areas where the efforts of individual states are not sufficient to implement certain policies.

4.2 Treaty of Lisbon

The Treaty of Lisbon was signed on December 13, 2007, after approximately 3 months of discussion, in the Portuguese capital. It was signed unanimously by all 27 EU member countries (Italy, France, Belgium, Holland, Luxembourg, Germany, Spain, Portugal, Poland, Great Britain, Romania, Hungary, Bulgaria, Slovenia, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Austria, Estonia, Latvia, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Greece, Ireland, Malta, Cyprus, Liechtenstein). But it will only really come into force in 2009, due to the blockade by Ireland. In fact, there the international treaties to be ratified must pass by referendum, which in 2008 gave a negative result. Only with a 2nd referendum, held the following year, the treaty was ratified also by Ireland and came into force on December 1, 2009, after the last country to ratify it (the Czech Republic).

It represents the culmination of a long process of revision of the European treaties, which began in the mid-1980s with the Single European Act. At first, the need to create the foundations of a European space without borders and then the prospect of enlargement to Central and Eastern European countries after the fall of the Berlin Wall have made a wide and deep reform of European institutions essential.

This new agreement established the need to develop permanent structured cooperation between the members of the Union, with the aim of strengthening their mutual cooperation in the military field. Thanks to this legal basis, with the initiative of the 25 European states to form the PSC (Permanent Structured Cooperation) established in 2017.

The provisions of the Treaty of Lisbon. After 15 years of coexistence between a Union born in Maastricht and the European Community born in Rome, the two entities have merged into a single European Union with legal personality. The values and objectives of the Union have consolidated those indicated by the European Constitution, with the significant addition of equality between men and women and with the clarification, laid down by the Intergovernmental Conference, that the Union will not be able to go beyond the competences assigned to it by the Treaty.

Finally, the division of tasks between States and the EU is clarified on the basis of the principle of subsidiarity by indicating the exclusive competences of the Union in the areas of customs union and competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market, common commercial policy and conservation of marine biological resources within the framework of the common fisheries policy, adding the federal competence of monetary policy for the States that have adopted the Euro as their single currency.

As we can see at the institutional level, the foreign and defense policy of the EU does not have a single face: different institutions are involved in the elaboration, decision-making and implementation

of this policy. This manifests the will of the European legislator to find a compromise between the need to make European foreign policy as communitarian as possible, removing it from unilateralism, and the pressures of certain more sovereign states and defenders of their own international weight. Several times Great Britain, clashing with France and Germany, has hindered the development towards a greater strategic autonomy of the EU.

Although European foreign policy is independent from that of individual states, for its formation and execution are necessary mechanisms of consultation between states within the European institutions (Council and European Council), for a convergence of actions and a common. The CFSP is a competence neither exclusive nor shared, but *sui generis*, in that it is limited only in its aims by the Treaties, but for the means it is up to the States to decide in the Council and European Council. A marginal role is foreseen for the European Parliament and the Commission. Procedurally, the Council decides on a proposal from the High Representative, after consultation with the European Parliament and approval by the Commission. The Council's decisions are binding.

We can therefore say that the characteristic of EU external action in the field of common foreign and defense policy is the prevalence of the intergovernmental method and the rule of unanimity in the decision-making process. This means that the particular interests of the states prevail in the decision-making phase, while the role of the institutions representing the common European interest remains marginal. Interesting aspect of the unanimity rule is the abstention, which does not affect the adoption of a decision unless it represents 1/3 of the states equivalent to 1/3 of the European population, in which case the decision is not taken.

The European Foreign Policy is also made up of a set of bilateral agreements with non-European countries involved in the management of migration flows. This is also intertwined with other areas of EU External Action, which we will examine in more detail in future articles. For now, it is sufficient to mention the past EU naval operation in the Mediterranean Sea, Operation Sophia is an example of integration of European military and police forces. This effort was also initiated at the instigation of the High Representative. To understand how the EU moves operationally, one must analyze CSDP as laid out below.

The operational arm of the EU's foreign and defense policy is the Common Security and Defense Policy (CSDP) and the EEAS (European External Action Service).

This policy provides the military and civilian means for interventions abroad.

At the Helsinki Summit in 1999, the project of a common defense dates back to the establishment of a European Military Force of Rapid Reaction for crisis management.

The Nice Summit in 2001 led to the formation of permanent political and military structures. On this occasion, the CSDP officially becomes part of the CFSP. Therefore, each Member State has to provide its own armed forces for Petersberg Missions. The procedure for intervention provides for a proposal by the High Representative or a Member State, followed by a Council decision that establishes the objectives, scope and modalities. States offer their contributions, military and civilian resources or multinational forces (groups of Member States). An example of a multinational force was EUROFOR (EUropean Rapid Operational FORCE), which brought together French, Italian, Spanish and Portuguese forces for interventions at the service of the EU and NATO in the Balkans in the early 2000s. Any action in the CFSP and CSDP must be compatible with the commitments undertaken within NATO.

The EEAS (European External Action Service), operational since 2011, is the support structure of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy and brings together officials from both the Commission and the Council, as well as diplomats from EU delegations abroad. Its staff therefore have different origins: the Directorate-General for the External Relations (DG RELEX) of the European Commission and the diplomatic corps of the Member States.

In addition, there are the EU Special Representatives (diplomats) sent to countries marked by crises and conflicts, which require the defense of European interests, peace and the rule of law.

The EU also cooperates with the organs of the United Nations and the specialized institutes of the United Nations, the Council of Europe, the OSCE (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe) and the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development).

In addition to the EU delegations in other international organizations, the EU's diplomatic representatives in third countries also coordinate and express the EU's positions, thus speaking on behalf of the Union in areas of its competence and in agreement with the member states. The problem arises especially at the multilateral level, when the EU, usually covering positions of observer, therefore without any influence in decision-making, must express the common position on certain issues that are not always unanimously agreed upon by its States.

However, before reaching a further technical-military development with the project of a real European Army, it is necessary to wait for a political will among the Member States to give up their sovereignty in the field of defense and security, without leaving the foreign and defense policy of the EU in limbo or impasse. This willingness seems to be lacking in the face of emerging sovereignism in Europe, which has, for example, led to the exit of the United Kingdom, which contributed to the defense sector even though it was always reluctant to the idea of a European army. Moreover, starting

from the assumption of complementarity between EU and NATO, duplication is not considered necessary. Greater strategic autonomy requires additional costs, while depending militarily on one's allies is certainly more economical.

Also, the High Representative Josep Borrell recalled that although the European Union needs greater autonomy, it is not and does not have the ambition to be a military union.

Despite the progress made in the area of European security and defence, there are many critical issues that do not allow for a unified foreign security policy. First of all, the European operational crisis management structure is still not very effective, and secondly, it is clear that member states continue to respond in too diverse a manner to international problems, choosing a nationalist rather than a community approach to problems.

4.3 Limits of UE foreign policy

The limits of a real European common foreign and security policy struggle to be something more and different than a difficult compromise between national foreign policies. The great Eastern powers, such as Russia or China, see France, Germany and the United Kingdom more in terms of international politics as national realities than as Europe as a whole. On the other hand, if you look at the history of American federal states, they firstly started with the integration of foreign policy, whereas in Europe they started with market integration, which is why foreign policy is the part most deeply rooted in national sovereignty, and therefore the most difficult to pool.

The transition to a common defence, which would give greater depth to the EU's strategic-military role at international level, and thus to its foreign and defence policy, requires the unanimous consent of the European Council, and if it is to be made the subject of enhanced cooperation, it requires the unanimous consent of the Council. It is therefore up to individual states to accept such a development, considering that some of them only need their own political and military weight in the context of the North Atlantic Alliance. Anyway, the effectiveness and coherence of the EU's foreign and defence policy are still not fully guaranteed, since although under the Biden presidency it seems to want to put the alliance with the European states back at the heart of its policy, the will to strengthen cooperation is not yet clear, as shown by the negotiations on the European Multiannual Financial Framework (2021-2027), which has greatly reduced defense budget.

Nevertheless, the EU remains a historic and extremely useful ally for the geopolitical purposes of the NATO and a leading defender of civil and human rights.

This declared return to Atlanticism by President Biden is in contrast to the previous administration, which was more self-centred and Pacific-focused. The Trumpian approach had, however, prompted Europeans to reconsider strengthening the Union in defence to make up for the great American absence and this is why chief of State such as Macron have proposed speeding up the processes for the integration of a real European army.

5. Results

5.1 The Yugosphere Theory

In 1991 Yugoslavia collapsed and the first conflict, which broke out in June, was between Slovenia and Serbia. It ended after only ten days with the independence of Slovenia.

The second, between Serbia and Croatia, broke out at the same time and recorded the same dynamics: Zagreb declared its exit from the Yugoslav Federation, Belgrade responded with arms. The difference was in the timing and intensity of the clashes. The Serb-Croat war, in fact, was characterised by serious devastation and ended only in 1995, when the Zagreb army, after a phase marked by a ceasefire, regained control of the territories of the Republic of Krajina, the Serb entity created by Belgrade within the Croatian borders.

After Slovenia and Croatia, it was the turn of Bosnia, where the war, which began in 1992 and ended three years later, was even more violent. Serbs, Muslims and Croats, the three national groups in Bosnia, faced each other mercilessly and more than 100,000 people were killed on the ground.

However, the war continued in the Balkans, in Kosovo, between 1998 and 1999. That war closed the decade of Balkan conflicts, laying the groundwork for Pristina to declare its secession from Serbia on 17 February 2008, ten years after the start of the fighting.

Kosovan independence was the last act in the process of disintegration of the former Yugoslavia. Today, there are seven nations in place of the former common homeland of the South Slavs. In addition to the aforementioned Slovenia, Croatia, Bosnia and Kosovo, to which Serbia must of course be added, Macedonia and Montenegro have also been granted the status of sovereign countries, but without bloodshed. The former at the end of 1991, the latter in May 2006.

Thirty years after the collapse of Yugoslavia, the situation in the various states has changed radically, although tensions remain high. However, new theories of economic and political integration, such as the Yugosphere theory, are beginning to emerge.

"Yugoslavia has long since ceased to exist, a Yugosphere is emerging in its place." With these words Tim Judah, expert and historical analyst at Economics, sanctioned the new evolution of the Balkan landscape almost twenty years after the outbreak of hostilities in the region. After years of reporting on clashes and divisions, the English journalist wanted to bring to light the silent and gradual process of reintegration that seems to have begun some time ago.

In the region, this new definition has aroused curiosity, stimulated reflection and opened debates on its validity and meaning. The term has entered by right into the specialized vocabulary but, above all, it has been widely used by the media, especially on the web.

As mentioned in the introduction of this research, the Balkans are fundamental for understanding the mechanisms of economic integration similar to those of the European Union. The phenomenon of the Yugosphere could give support to those theories that define the European Union as a *sui generis* actor or civilian power, and how its model is inspiring the emergence of new similar models.

The starting point of Judah's reflection is, of course, the economic one. He notes how a common market is increasingly being restructured in the area, considered unique first and foremost by the economic actors that operate there. However, the pages of the article go even further, re-evaluating the social and cultural commonalities of the region's populations, underlining how strong are the correspondences of daily life, ranging from language to gastronomy to music.

A similarity that we can relate to the case of the European Union, and as mentioned earlier in Putnam's theory of the two-level game, state policies resemble a two-level game: that is, one of domestic politics and the other of international politics. Subjects who participate in the game of domestic politics also participate when they are engaged in negotiations with subjects outside the state, i.e., when they have to obtain a decision that they will have to enforce internationally. And, vice versa, when they participate in the international political game, they must succeed in obtaining decisions that will be well received within their own country. It thus emerges that a state's domestic and foreign policies are essentially the same thing. In fact, those who take decisions in the two areas are the same people, which is why it is necessary for the heads of state of these Balkan states to always take decisions that are consistent in terms of both economic integration and national interest, again demonstrating empirically that a Communitarian foreign policy is impossible to achieve because it is incompatible on several levels.

Finally, there is no domestic policy decision that does not have international relevance and vice versa. Similarly, to those of the European Union, the states of the former Yugoslavia have adapted to the effects of globalization, because the economic, financial, social, cultural, health interdependencies are increasing more and more, and it is clear that these states tend to a kind of unification by seeking a union between various political subjects, through economic integration.

5.2 UE role in the Balkans

The wars that resulted from the dissolution of federal Yugoslavia are closely intertwined with the process of European integration. In February 1992, the Heads of State and Government of the European Community signed the Treaty on European Union in Maastricht. In February 1992, President Izetbegovic's decision to hold a referendum on the independence of Bosnia-Herzegovina was the trigger for the inter-ethnic war, the dramatic outcome of the earlier conflicts in Slovenia and Croatia.

The Union in the European context in the aftermath of the end of the Cold War and amid speculation about the future operational capabilities of the nascent CFSP could and should have managed diplomatically or militarily a crisis that had appeared at the very heart of the Continent. But it was an aspiration. Because European governments failed to interpret events adequately, to draw up Peace Plans consistent with the ongoing dynamics of ethnic cleansing, to manage and coordinate missions on the ground and, most importantly, they showed a substantial lack of will to use force. This lack of will had very serious consequences with the violence against civilians that occurred throughout the Yugoslav wars.

Part of my research intends to retrace the key stages of the European Union's role in the crisis and stabilisation of Bosnia and Herzegovina highlights the thesis that the limitations and negligence of international involvement are partly explained by the fact that in the aftermath of the end of the Cold War a delineated security organization was lacking in the UE, which still today does not allow the creation of a coherent and communitarian foreign policy.

The Bosnian theatre of war even became a political laboratory for experimenting with different configurations of this strategy: the unsuccessful attempts to intervene with international organisations other than NATO led European governments to the conclusion that only through the military involvement of the United States could the crisis finally reach a conclusion.

The intervention in Bosnia-Herzegovina was the first out-of-area intervention by NATO, an organisation that thus became the seal of a close political symbiosis between European Union and the United States in terms of the external projection of force.

The limitations and negligence in the conflict phase are also related to the lack of a real international and European interest, since without a strategy in EU foreign policy, interests in the Balkans remain purely economic and not strategic.

It is no coincidence that the European Union began to acquire relevance in the area only after the end of the conflict, through the management of peace-keeping and the delegation of international

organisations and diplomatic corps of the European Union. This is a clear demonstration not only of the use of European soft power, but also of the symbiotic relationship with the United States that covers the organisation's gap in security and defence and the limited means of hard power at its disposal.

In support of my analysis, it is necessary to highlight the action taken by the European Union since the resolution of the Kosovo crisis: The Stability Pact represents a clear change of approach, methods and instruments towards South-Eastern Europe. The European Union channeled the flow of international aid and development credits under joint coordination in such a way as to link it to the strengthening of the reform process of political and economic systems. A common European strategy was finally born, reflecting the interest in expanding the borders of the single market, an enlargement that was an effective stabilising factor for the entire region.

If the European Union will successfully integrate a hypothetical macro-regional organisation in the Balkans in the future, Europe itself would certainly gain. This is because the European Union internally works with regional logic (Visegrad group, Baltic countries and Benelux), ergo, the European Union would also gain by bringing under its economic influence a macro-region of fundamental importance and historically under the Russian sphere of influence.

As quoted above in my introduction, Britain's Alan Milward has argued that European integration, far from eroding national sovereignty, has also helped states to recover it through other means, the same being true of the Balkan states.

Italy, for example, has important bilateral relations with the Balkan states due to historical ties and emigration, as well as enjoying an enormous cultural heritage, very useful for soft power.

These factors could exert a considerable influence on the region through the support of the European Union, with the creation of effective transversal institutions and organisations.

A new economic and commercial collaboration through railways and ports on the Ionian Sea shore, massive investment campaigns to finance EU projects for job creation and infrastructure, the Balkan area could have a renaissance not only in economic terms, but also in cultural, legal and political terms influenced by the new hypothetical European integration process.

The Balkan peninsula is a land of competition rather than cooperation between European countries themselves, i.e. between Italy, Germany and France. This competition, which is more or less reasonable, is the result of intergovernmental initiatives that overlap one another and generate confusion and paralysis. It is sufficient, in fact, to recall how jagged the framework of actors and institutional and international platforms that have operated in the Balkan area over time, to realise

how many different perspectives have coexisted and still coexist today: QUINT, an inclusive quintet of Western powers (the US, Italy, Germany, France and the United Kingdom) in which an overall political vision of the region relating to peace and security issues prevails, the apparatus of the European Union, committed to a strategy of enlargement and accession, the so-called "Berlin Process" (led by Germany) and the older and more solid "Central European Initiative", an evolution of the "Quadrilateral" that arose in November 1989 at the instigation of the then Italian government.

A scenario that well highlights how there is a clear intra-EU competition, even before that with international partners such as Russia and China, which is based on the search for trade and investment opportunities that the Western Balkans region offers to the various EU players, also by virtue of its particular geographical location. In the last 10 years, total trade between the EU and the Western Balkan countries amounted to more than EUR 43 billion, an increase of 80% in less than a decade. These are concrete, tangible interests that often remain in the background compared to the grand strategic plans proclaimed in the official declarations of the Council and the European Commission, with the result of increasing the EU's capability-expectations gap. The problems of Balkan enlargement are therefore political and bureaucratic, with the latter often stemming from the former, but not infrequently testifying to the conflicting prevalence of practice over reason. Europe must demonstrate farsightedness and political wisdom in the negotiation processes. However, it is the logic of Brussels to manage the matter in a self-referential manner and that of its bureaucratic structures that try to influence and control not only the accession processes but also the internal politics of countries that, moreover, are not yet members of the Union (the so-called Bruxelles effect). Let us take the case of Serbia, one of the key countries for Europe in the region and the de facto frozen negotiations concerning its accession. Belgrade is still waiting for its accession to the European Union, which is a long way off in time, and in the meantime has drawn up a series of international economic agreements with criteria that do not comply with EU directives. However, it is also logical in Serbian national interests that if China provides the necessary funding for the construction of the Belgrade-Budapest high-speed railway, the government will gladly accept.

The European Union must find in reasonableness its compass to manage the thorny issue of the integration of the Balkan countries, it must pivot on realities like the Serbian one, overcoming at the root also the intra-European conflict between pro-Croatians and pro-Serbs that accompanies the regional dynamics from the collapse of Yugoslavia onwards and it must try to leverage new factors and scenarios emerging in the geopolitical scenario such as the Yugosphere, to push towards a new regional integration in the fastest and most pragmatic way possible.

5.3 Main issues:

In this section we will analyse the three main obstacles blocking the European Union from becoming a unified global actor.

- Lack of strategic autonomy
- Not a real sovereign army
- Conflicting national interests among the member states

5.3.1 Lack of strategic autonomy:

When we look at the European Union's action in foreign policy, weakness and confusion are often perceived. The history of Brussels' international role is, in fact, full of episodes of indecision and hesitation that have always undermined the EU as a leading global actor. Brussels has often played an undoubtedly important role, but only by following in the footsteps of some other superpower or as a major player in predominantly multilateral contexts. The classic example of this has always been the Atlantic alliance. The relationship between the EU and the US has almost always been excellent, but also characterised by Washington's superiority. The defence field is where this asymmetric relationship is most evident: through NATO, the US has always contributed more to the defence of the continent than the EU. The Union has therefore often taken on the role of a supporting actor in international affairs. In essence, European strategic autonomy can no longer be based on the short-sighted and illusory vision of independence or of an equal transatlantic partnership in external security and defence matters, but must follow the more difficult but necessary path of a global multilateralism that focuses on the challenges of today's world without pursuing the tragic objective of replacing a sum of state nationalisms with the continental isolationism of European nationalism.

5.3.2 Not a sovereign army

As explained in the last chapter, the definition of the EU's foreign policy areas is left to the intergovernmental method: the European Council, called upon to identify the strategic interests, objectives and general guidelines of the Union in foreign policy, is composed of the heads of state or government of the member states. The Council, on the other hand, called upon to draw up the common foreign and security policy by taking the decisions necessary to implement the general guidelines defined by the European Council, is the body that represents the governments of the member states.

As the European Union is not a state, it does not have a real sovereign army, as the European multinational army has a limited mandate in the area of defence, with the sole role of exploring the issue of defence granted by the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997).

Not having full sovereignty over armed forces, some EU states can and do make multilateral defence arrangements outside the EU structures. The EU acts through the Common Foreign and Security Policy, although there are states such as Denmark that have chosen not to cooperate with it and some states are prevented from doing so by issues of neutrality, which makes it difficult to create a genuine Common Foreign and Security Policy. Forces under EU command are mainly used in peace missions, in which the EU has a great tradition of participation.

5.3.3 Conflictive national interests between member states.

The third and final reason why the EU's foreign policy is ineffective in practice stems from the fact that its implementation is left both to the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy and to the member states themselves, which will always have opposing interests, a case in point being the competition between the Italian multinational ENI and the French Total in Africa, or the diplomatic chaos that arose after the Yugoslav wars and the recognition of Kosovo.

But speaking about the case of Lybia that is more recents, we can see as the defence of the national interests of Italy (energy and migration) and France (terrorism and regional balances, especially in the Sahel) have limited the European Union influence that, with the worsening of the crisis in the last years, could have played a more decisive role as an important actor on the ground.

5.4 European Integration as means of power

With the problems illustrated above, regarding the creation of a European community policy, we can therefore come to the conclusion that European integration would not represent the crisis of the nation state, as argued by federalist scholars and pro-European activists, but its strengthening and adaptation to a new international reality, as well as a coherent response to the globalisation process, through the use of forms of partial economic and legal integration.

In the light of this thesis, the prospect of building a United States of Europe or, at any rate, the creation of a federal state, as originally conceived by the Founding Fathers, would seem a distant utopia.

Returning precisely to the debate on the creation of a single European state, the current political debate is unfortunately dominated by two categories: Eurosceptics and Euroenthusiasts.

These two groups are united by the idea that European integration leads to the dissolution of state sovereignty. This idea, however, seems doubly untenable.

The idea of a dissolution of state sovereignty is untenable, first of all, in its premises. The sovereignty whose dissolution is lamented or celebrated, in fact, has never had the contours that its apologists or critics have imagined.

There is another reason why the idea of the complete disappearance of sovereignty does not seem sustainable. That idea is based on the premise that the process of European integration has led to a real expropriation of the sovereignty of the member states of the Union, which has been handed over to the European institutions. Although this highlights a very important point, things are not in the extreme terms commonly imagined.

First of all, it should never be forgotten that, the states are still the main actors in the European Union that define, to a considerable extent, the timeframe, functions and possible contents of Community regulation. This means that it is the states that govern themselves through the pactual instrument of the treaties, deciding whether, when and how much to enter the integration process. In this way, however, it is precisely the classic instrument of inter-national law, of law made by nation states and for nation states, that allows or prevents the integration process from moving forward. Furthermore, in accordance with the Vienna Convention, it is the states that determine and use the constitutional rules to be complied with when ratifying new treaties or amendments to those in force.

It is the states, then, that remain the protagonists of the Community institutions, both because the European Parliament is still far from being comparable to the representative assemblies known and theorised by constitutional law, and because it is the states that directly make up the Community institutions or choose their members, as in the case of the Commission.

We have several examples of how European integration has helped countries in backward economic conditions to change their condition and increase their economic and social welfare, such as Spain, Poland and most recently Croatia.

In the case of Spain, when the then president of the government, the socialist Felipe Gonzáles, signed the Treaty of Accession to the EEC on 12th June 1985, the Iberian country received billions of euros in aid, something very similar to a Marshall Plan. This aid was used to create jobs and infrastructure, making Spain one of the biggest recipients of EU funds.

During the transition, therefore, the European model of democracy had exercised a strong attraction on the Spanish reality, to the point of leading various scholars to affirm that the construction of a democratic political system and the objective of full integration had been but two sides of the same process.

The most visible change in this situation can also be seen in the increase in population, which has been matched by a parallel growth in employment, despite the fact that in recent months the international crisis has pushed unemployment levels to very high levels. These changes in the way of life have also resulted in an increase in life expectancy. But the importance of Community integration for Spain is not only in the economic or demographic field, but also in the political one, especially in the transition to democracy.

Since the end of the 1970s, in fact, the Iberian country has painlessly passed through the delicate phase of the transition to democracy. Democratic Spain was built at the same time as it was integrating into the European Community.

In the case of Poland, however, the transition to a liberal state was different.

The fall of the Wall and the consequent dissolution of the Comecon, which pushed the Soviet Union to sell its raw materials at market prices, instead of ceding them at fixed prices to its former satellites, converted the Polish production system into an obsolete one and pushed the governments that alternated from then on, including those under ex-communist leadership, to accelerate the process of restructuring and privatisation that began in 1992 and was facilitated by two and a half billion dollars in funding from the World Bank (WorldBank, 1992).

As early as 1996, Poland had already entered the economic orbit of the EU, to which it allocated two thirds of its exports and from which just under half of its imports came. Half of this trade originated or ended in Germany, but the goods involved were of low quality: trade with Poland accounted for only 2% of the German balance of trade (WorldBank, 1996). The Polish economy remained highly

unbalanced, the poor state of the system and the weakness of the internal market prevented local companies from expanding.

However, thanks to the improvements brought about by German investments and the use of European funds for infrastructure and logistics, goods manufactured in Poland have grown not only in quality and quantity, but also in cost-effectiveness compared to all EU countries that have had the euro, Europe's leading single currency, since 2001. Polish products have won new outlets on the continent, and at the first signs of economic crisis exports were protected by an immediate devaluation of the local currency, the zloty, which safeguarded competitiveness.

In both cases, we can see how Spain and Poland, two countries with an authoritarian past and economic backwardness, were able to rapidly benefit from economic integration, not only in economic terms but also in strategic terms.

In the case of Spain, in less than 20 years the Iberian country has become a modern European democracy and a key strategic country for NATO throughout the Cold War.

In the case of Poland, we can see how this country went from being a satellite country of Moscow for the duration of the Cold War and how after the collapse of the Soviet Union, the European Union and NATO filled the vacuum left by Russian influence with massive economic investment from the EU and military support from NATO.

In both cases we can see how European integration has taken place, satisfying national interests, including the economic and strategic interests of both states.

We can therefore say that, as Putnam argues, although foreign policy may be at odds with EU interests on several levels, by delegating some economic policies to the supranational level, governments can increase their power, gaining additional resources of an economic nature against their internal adversaries. European integration thus responds above all to the interests of states and advances to the extent that the interests of states are satisfied.

If we want to formulate a hypothesis on the future of one of the states of the Yugosphere, we could instead take the example of Croatia, which has been part of the European Union since 2013.

As already stated in the previous chapters, the European states would gain a great deal in political terms if they had a more convinced and consistent policy towards the Balkans. On the one hand, by simply stabilising within their sphere of influence an area that was previously unstable, the EU institutions could offer a permanent arena where conflicts, which have always ended up dragging in and involving the rest of Europe, would be discussed and managed peacefully.

A more democratic arena beyond the now defunct Iron Curtain, where Balkan states like Croatia could also make their transition to modern European social democracy.

Moreover, by exploiting the strategic advantages that this new integration allows, such as the construction of trade and energy supply routes to and from the East and the Caucasus, once again confirming the theory about the benefit of European economic integration.

For this to happen as quickly as possible, the Union's international policy will have to stop being the sum of national interests and become a fully-fledged supranational management of foreign affairs, and start seeing certain areas with a more macro-regional and less centralised perspective.

5.5 EU as sui generis power

In order to understand the fundamental characteristics of the EU's external relations, it is necessary to look at how they have gradually defined themselves, changing as the integration process has progressed. The way in which the EU political system has been defined explains its complexity and sui generis form, with different powers, decision-making rules and distribution of sovereignty according to the scope of policy. At the same time, the gradual internal transformation and the attempt to respond to external challenges also explains the specificities of the Union as an international actor: great resources of power in the economic sphere and permanent weaknesses in the political sphere.

Let us briefly look at the characteristics of this role of the EEC-EU as a model and promoter actor of regional integration, in order to ask whether the European model is really exportable and what are the limits of the interregional policy of the EU.

Since the early 1990s, the end of bipolarity and the pressures of globalisation processes have led to a search for regional responses to the needs of the new international context. There has thus been an exponential increase in what is now known as the process of 'regionalisation', resulting in new practices of interregionalism that encompass bilateral or multilateral international relations in the traditional sense. The EU has almost always served as a model in the establishment of these regional organisations, while at the same time financially assisting their creation.

However, although considered a source of inspiration for other regional integration processes, the EU integration model is difficult to replicate by other international organisations.

The Mercosur, although explicitly inspired by the EU, remains a free trade area with aspects of a customs union, functioning purely on an intergovernmental basis, and with the possibility of enlargement not yet realised. The AU (African Union) has institutions and aims similar to those of the EU, but it remains a process of regional cooperation, where national prerogatives are dominant and where a real devolution of powers to supranational institutions has not yet been achieved. The institutions of the Asian regional organisations are also weak, with purely economic aims (Apec or Asean), even if their powers are gradually being extended to sectors such as security.

One might think that these differences between the EU and the other regional organisations are only due to the more recent history of the new regional organisations, but this is most likely a weak explanation. There are in fact structural differences that characterise the region concerned and the regional organisation that inevitably led to a different path of the integration process.

The distinctive feature of the common commercial policy is the combination of a multilateral and regional approach. Indeed, the European institutions have always supported the multilateral

regulation of trade, which took hold after World War II, and at the same time the establishment of the single market pushed other international players (the US in particular) to support a further step in the liberalisation process.

On the other hand, the EU, as we have seen above, also adopts a very pronounced regional approach and has the largest number of preferential trade agreements of any WTO member. Although clearly in conflict with the principle of non-discrimination promoted by the WTO, preferential treatment is allowed under existing legislation in the case of regional trade agreements such as customs unions or free trade areas. Precisely because of its importance in international trade, the EU can use its trade policy as its main foreign policy instrument through access to the European market, economic cooperation and financial aid. A case in point is the promotion of democracy through the so-called conditionality clause which, is now included in all EU trade agreements.

The conditionality clause is absolutely in line with the structure of the European Union and is a clear example of how the organisation, through soft power, tries to influence other states to adopt its own regulations in the economic and civil sphere (Brussels effect), a coherent evolution of Europe as a "civil power" theorised by Duchêne.

Conclusion

It has been very interesting to analyse the different theories formulated about the European Union, their evolution and their concrete application.

However, it should be kept in mind, that there is no theory that has absolute truth or that can make exact predictions about the future of the European Union.

The aim of this research is to show that the European Union is far from forming a single multilingual and multi-ethnic state, as the founding fathers theorised, but it has nevertheless undergone a *sui generis* evolution that has gradually modified the structure of the organisation.

Moreover, the theories set out in the course of the work are not at odds with each other, but rather the opposite, each theory being perfectly consistent with the logic by which the EU functions.

We can see that in modern theories, the EU has begun to evolve its structure in such a way as to gradually become a relevant geopolitical actor in economic and legal terms.

As a laboratory and a *sui generis* power, the EU presents the difficulties of a political system where the elements of governance are in some areas greater than those of government, which necessarily represents a challenge, but also a problem, both for the efficiency of the system (a system of governance is often less efficient than one of government), but also and above all for its democratic legitimacy and consequently for the trust that citizens place in it. Both limitations risk becoming insurmountable obstacles to further progress in the integration process, leading not only to greater efficiency, but also and above all to a greater sense of common belonging on the part of citizens.

From the above picture it can be deduced that the EU has much more international presence and power than the general public generally gives it credit for. However, there are undoubted elements of weakness, some shared with other international players, others specifically European.

Faced with such a complex picture, what future can be expected? The scenarios that lie ahead are very different, depending on the capacity that the EU and its member states will have to use the comparative advantage that the Union derives from being in itself a laboratory for processes of political transformation: comparative power with respect to the great emerging powers and the challenges of contemporary politics can only be used if we do not stop believing in the resource constituted by the fact that the EU can be an experiment in multilateral governance that looks forward and not backwards - to nationalistic and state-centric models of response, as is increasingly the case. This does not imply imagining a future European federal state, but a complex political system in which community decision-making mechanisms are strengthened, or in which the power of veto of the states is limited, coordination between different policies is strengthened, and the EU's unitary

external representation is reinforced. All of this has begun to be done in the *Lisbon Treaty*, but what cannot be done with the institutional architecture is much more fundamental, it is a reversal of the direction in which the political culture of European integration has drifted, constantly challenged by the renationalisation of politics and the sense of identity, by the abandonment of any political project on what the EU is or should be, and by the pathological lack of a leadership with planning skills.

If the international role of the EU has been the result of a process of internal construction, it is only by responding effectively to the problems of the latter that the European Union will really be able to assume a major role in international politics, beyond that which derives from its mere existence as an area of integration, peace and prosperity.

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